

Original Research

Study on Determinants Influencing Driving Through EEG Technology

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Abstract

Driving safety is an important factor in avoiding traffic accidents, and a driver's physiological and psychological states play an important role while driving. This article, which uses electroencephalography (EEG) technology, examines the EEG signal characteristics under various driving conditions and the relationship between driving performance and influencing factors such as drunk driving, mental fatigue, physical fatigue, and emotional fluctuations. This study identifies key EEG indicators, to quantify the driver's state and reveal their relationship with driving performance, providing a scientific basis for real-time driver state monitoring. The findings validate the rationality of current traffic regulations on drunk driving while highlighting the potential risks of physical fatigue and emotional fluctuations, addressing gaps in existing regulations. Overall, this article uses EEG technology to investigate the neural mechanisms underlying dangerous driving states, as well as to provide new quantitative methods and theoretical support for driver state monitoring. Future research will concentrate on improving EEG monitoring devices, integrating multimodal data, and developing real-time driving safety monitoring systems to improve overall road traffic safety.

Keywords: EEG signals; drunk driving; fatigued driving

Introduction

In daily life, traffic accidents are a common and dangerous event, and the safety of driving behavior is one of the important factors affecting the occurrence of traffic accidents. However, people's understanding and reaction process towards driving behavior are not fully clear, which poses certain difficulties for research in the field of traffic safety. Therefore, studying driving behavior and its influencing factors is of great significance for improving traffic safety levels.

As a non-invasive and real-time biological signal measurement method, EEG technology can provide information about the cognitive state and neural activity of drivers during the driving process. Previous studies have shown that the brainwaves of drivers can reflect changes in driving conditions, such as driving fatigue, drunk driving, drowsiness, etc. For example, Lin et al. (2007) used EEG technology to study drivers' cognitive responses to changes in traffic signals, demonstrating the potential application of EEG technology in evaluating drivers' cognitive responses. Eujuchan's research also indicates the impact of drinking driving on brainwaves in driving behavior, further highlighting the correlation between driving behavior and brainwaves.

However, the current application of EEG technology in driving behavior analysis is not sufficient. Although

some related studies already exist, there are some limitations, such as a lack of in-depth research on cognitive differences in different driving behaviors, a lack of systematic analysis of EEG features specific to driving scenarios, and quantification of various influencing factors. Therefore, it is necessary to further study the impact and correlation of EEG technology in driving behavior analysis to fill the existing research gap.

2. Literature Review

The detection methods for fatigue driving can generally be divided into subjective detection methods and objective detection methods. At present, the mainstream methods for determining fatigue driving in domestic and foreign research are still objective detection methods, mainly including the following methods.

In terms of physiological signal detection, foreign researchers such as SukardiSuba et al. (2019) found through analyzing data from 76 drivers on public highways in Sweden that as the driver's fatigue level increases, heart rate decreases and heart rate variability (HRV) increases. Fu et al. (2016) used a hidden Markov model combined with electroencephalography (EEG), electromyography (EMG), and respiratory signals to construct a dynamic fatigue detection model, demonstrating that this method can effectively identify driver fatigue status. In addition, Wang et al. (2018) used power spectral density (PSD) and sample entropy (SampEn) of electrocardiogram signals to detect mental fatigue. The experimental results showed that this method was highly consistent with the changes in driver reaction time and exhibited good predictive performance.

Domestic research has also achieved certain results in physiological signals. Zeng Chao et al. (2020) compared gender differences between awake and fatigued states by analyzing the nonlinear characteristics of HRV, and found that the variability and complexity of ANS increased, and there were significant gender differences. In addition, some studies have focused on the frequency band changes of EEG signals, such as Wang et al. (2019) who found that the activity level of Theta waves significantly increased under fatigue conditions, while Beta waves decreased. A study on long-distance transportation drivers shows that male drivers have more pronounced reactions to fatigue than female drivers.

In terms of detecting driver behavior characteristics, foreign research mainly adopts non-contact visual technology. For example, Waleed et al. (2018) designed a modular detection method based on head rotation angle, which can identify fatigue driving early and has good robustness. Scholars found significant differences in values before and after fatigue through indicators such as eye closure time, percentage of eye closure (PERCLOS), and blink frequency. Zhang et al. (2012) used computer vision to monitor real-time features of the driver's eyes, mouth, and head, and fused different variable states through a Bayesian network model to achieve fatigue detection. Domestic research has also made progress in behavior detection, such as Nie et al. evaluating driving fatigue through indicators such as PERCLOS and blink frequency, and the results are consistent with foreign research.

The detection of vehicle operating status is also one of the research focuses. Abroad, Takei et al. (2023) processed the steering wheel angle signal through Fourier transform and wavelet transform to determine the driver's fatigue state. Wu et al. (2019) designed a real-time detection system for lane departure and distance from the preceding vehicle, which sends warning signals to the driver by calculating the angle of the lane boundary. In China, researchers mainly detect fatigue through indicators such as steering wheel angle, speed, and lane departure, but there is relatively insufficient integration with complex system models.

In the study of EEG waves and driver behavior, most of them are based on the normal EEG activity of drivers, and then compared with EEG in different states. Research has found that the activity levels of Delta and Theta waves are correlated with driving fatigue. The activity level of Theta waves significantly increases with increasing fatigue, while the activity level of Beta waves decreases after the onset of driving fatigue. Based on the study of waveform activity changes, the ratio of different frequency bands of brain waves and combinations is often used to reflect the situation of EEG activity. For example, there are various forms such as Theta/Beta , $\text{Theta}/(\text{Alpha}+\text{Beta})$, $(\text{Theta}+\text{Alpha})/\text{Beta}$, and $(\text{Theta}+\text{Alpha})/(\text{Alpha}+\text{Beta})$. The series of equations includes Theta waves as slow wave activity and Beta waves as fast wave activity. Many cognitive tasks, such as math calculations and behavioral inhibitory tasks like N-back, have been found to increase Theta and Beta waves in the frontal region of the brain when individuals experience cognitive load. At the same time, the power of Theta waves can characterize the degree of interference experienced by drivers during normal driving. A driving simulation test was conducted on the driver to investigate the relationship between the captured EEG signals and driving fatigue. The research results showed that even in simple traffic

environments, the driver gradually developed fatigue after driving for more than 30 minutes. A study conducted in Zhejiang on the characteristics of driving fatigue among long-distance transportation drivers by increasing Theta and Beta frequencies found that men had better performance in reflecting driving fatigue than women.

With the development of digital technology, more and more complex system methods are being used to quantify brain function. Entropy is the most commonly used method to balance the complexity of the brain. Based on entropy parameters, the sequential changes of complex systems can be reflected, and the trend of system changes can be studied. Therefore, entropy theory can be applied to evaluate brain functional states. Pincus [18] proposed approximate entropy, which enables its algorithm to perform calculations on samples with small data volumes and is applicable to the analysis of different collected physiological signals. Richman et al. (2000) proposed the concept of sample entropy by improving approximate entropy, expanding the application scope of entropy theory. Costa et al. (2002) proposed that it is possible to demonstrate the complexity of long time series through the study of multi-scale sample entropy. Many scholars have also demonstrated through their own research results that evaluating the characteristics of human EEG signals at different scales is of great significance.

Overall, research both domestically and internationally has achieved certain results in fatigue driving detection, but there are still some shortcomings. Firstly, existing research mostly focuses on fatigue states under a single condition, such as long-term driving, and pays less attention to changes in EEG signals under different driving conditions, especially under conditions such as emotional fluctuations and drunk driving, which are still relatively lacking. Secondly, the detection of physiological signals, driving behavior, and vehicle status is often conducted independently, lacking a comprehensive detection model that integrates multidimensional analysis. In addition, with the development of digital technology, complex system quantification methods such as entropy theory are gradually being applied to EEG signal analysis. However, their application in fatigue driving detection is still in its infancy, and multi-scale analysis of EEG complexity is not yet in-depth. Finally, there is currently limited research on fatigue under multiple factor superposition conditions, which fails to fully reveal the coupling relationship between different factors.

3. Data Processing and Analysis

The St The EEGTM. Altaire EEG acquisition system is a 32 channel wearable electroencephalogram (EEG) system. EEG signal is a very weak bioelectric signal, which is easily interfered by signals such as eye electricity, electromyography, and mains electricity during the process of EEG acquisition. Therefore, it is extremely important to filter and denoise the collected data after EEG signal acquisition. This study used the EEGLAB plugin in Matlab for data preprocessing.

Firstly, examine the waveform of the brainwave and manually observe whether each group of brainwave data is complete, whether there are abnormal fluctuations or channels that have not been collected, whether there are large-scale abnormalities in the waveform, and whether the brainwave signal is valid.

Baseline calibration is mainly used to correct data skewness, which can improve baseline differences caused by low-frequency drift or artifacts, making EEG images clearer and easier to observe. By utilizing the Remove Baseline feature in EEGLAB, baseline calibration can be automatically completed.

The EEG data collected in this article are all over 30 minutes long. When the sampling rate is too high, it is not conducive to computer analysis, and when the sampling rate is too low, the details in the data are difficult to preserve. Due to the fact that the EEG signals analyzed in this experiment mainly consist of delta waves, alpha waves, and beta waves with frequencies ranging from 4Hz to 32Hz, in order to ensure sufficient detail in the EEG data, a sampling rate of 512 was used for experimental data processing in this paper.

In this study, descriptive statistical analysis mainly revealed the EEG characteristics under different driving states through three aspects: EEG waveform, kurtosis, and Pearson correlation coefficient.

EEG waveform is an important tool for displaying the temporal changes of EEG signals. By drawing EEG waveforms under different driving conditions, the amplitude and frequency changes of signals can be visually observed, thereby identifying differences in specific states. For example, drunk driving may exhibit significant low-frequency fluctuations, while fatigue driving may be accompanied by higher frequency noise. By comparing these waveform diagrams, researchers can identify characteristic patterns of brain electrical activity, providing a foundation for further analysis.

In the figure, a represents the relative power change in the alpha band, b represents the relative power change in the beta band, c represents the power change in the theta band, and d represents the change in the fatigue factor R value. "-0" in the figure represents the time before drinking alcohol, and "+0" represents the instantaneous time after drinking alcohol. The analysis results of the relative power of each band according to the timeline are as follows:

-0~+0: The changes in various frequency bands before and after acute low alcohol consumption are mainly manifested as a decrease in alpha power and an increase in beta power. Alcohol stimulates the brain to produce a momentary sense of excitement, and a large number of beta waves appear in the cerebral cortex, resulting in a relative decrease in alpha; The frequency of theta waves appearing in the human brain is high when drowsiness occurs. During the experiment of low alcohol consumption, the subjects experienced less drowsiness, so the overall power value of theta waves is not high (only about 25% of the alpha band power), and the change is not significant.

+0-120: Within 120 minutes after acute low alcohol consumption, the power in the alpha band gradually increases and the power in the beta band gradually decreases. The stimulating effect of alcohol on the brain gradually weakens, and the excitability of the cerebral cortex decreases step by step until it returns to normal levels. During the experiment, the subjects wore electrode caps. Due to the time constraints of the experiment, the subjects also experienced a certain degree of fatigue. The fatigue factor R value was basically consistent with the trend of the alpha band, indicating that the impact of acute low alcohol consumption on the cerebral cortex is mainly concentrated in the mid frequency band (8-13Hz), as the alpha band is easily stimulated by external factors and breaks its original state. After acute low alcohol consumption, the fatigue level of the cerebral cortex instantly drops to the lowest point, and then gradually increases, reaching normal levels around 90 minutes after drinking.

From the graph, it can be clearly seen that the frequency bands decrease with the increase of alcohol consumption time. In normal driving conditions, the gamma wave has the highest entropy value and is more complex, followed by the beta wave; At the beginning, delta waves have the lowest complexity, but after driving for a long time, their complexity gradually increases compared to other low-frequency waves. The driver's drowsiness is gradually increasing. Finally, each frequency band is basically in a stable state after 90 minutes.

5. Conclusion

This study conducted an in-depth analysis of driver behavior and its influencing factors based on electroencephalography (EEG) technology, aiming to reveal the cognitive and physiological changes of drivers in different driving states through EEG signals. Research has shown that the role of EEG signals in reflecting drivers' attention, emotional state, fatigue level, and driving behavior cannot be ignored. EEG signals are closely related to driving behavior: in the driver's EEG signals, changes in frequency bands such as alpha waves, beta waves, theta waves, and delta waves can reflect the driver's cognitive state and driving behavior in specific contexts. For example, after drinking alcohol, the driver's beta wave activity significantly increases, while under fatigue conditions, the power of theta and delta waves significantly increases. The influencing factors of driving behavior: This study shows that mental fatigue, physical fatigue, and emotional fluctuations all significantly affect the driver's EEG signals, which in turn affect their driving behavior. In situations of mental fatigue and significant emotional fluctuations, the driver's reaction time is prolonged, attention is diverted, leading to a decrease in driving safety.

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